

Adopting Genre-Based Writing Pedagogy in Japan: Challenges and Possibilities from a Teacher's Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This longitudinal case study explores a language teacher's experiences and perspectives towards adopting genre-based writing pedagogy. More specifically, the article examines how the teacher dealt with the pedagogy while attempting to improve his English writing teaching in a high school in Japan. The author was involved in the research by providing theoretical input and observing the teacher's practice in the classroom. Teacher interviews and teacher journals were collected. It was found that year-long support changed the teacher's attitude towards genre-based literacy pedagogy. It was also identified that there were difficulties in adopting the pedagogy in relation to the participant's teaching environment and the benefits of utilising an artificial intelligence (AI) tool. The AI tool was helpful for the teacher in providing corrective feedback to learners.

Keywords: interviews, genre-based writing pedagogy, systemic functional linguistics, teacher development

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past 20 years, research on genre-based writing pedagogy has developed significantly in the field of Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL). In their systematic literature review, Zhai and Razali (2023) concluded that genre-based writing pedagogy is now widely employed worldwide. Similarly, numerous studies have explored how this approach enhances learners' writing skills (e.g., Mauludin, 2020; Uzun & Topkaya, 2019; Zhang & Zhang, 2021). While previous research has primarily focused on the effectiveness of pedagogy in writing instruction, the accessibility of this approach for language teachers remains an under-researched area. In other words, existing studies on genre-based literacy pedagogy have not thoroughly investigated language teachers' experiences in adopting this approach. Genre-based writing pedagogy often requires a solid foundation in theoretical knowledge (e.g., de Oliveira & Lan, 2014; Emilia & Hamied, 2015). For example, pedagogy developed within systemic functional linguistics (see Martin & Rose, 2008) employs concepts such as register and metafunctions to examine language features and choices in writing. Nagao (2019) argues that it is not clear which aspect of the pedagogy is helpful for teachers.

Research on teachers' perspectives and experiences with genre-based writing pedagogy is warranted to assess its accessibility. A longitudinal study on teachers' experiences can reveal the possibilities and limitations of implementing genre-based writing pedagogy. By examining a teacher's perspective in an English as a foreign language (EFL) context, the study can shed light on this underexplored aspect of genre-based writing pedagogy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Genre-based writing pedagogy

This study adopts the concept of genre developed by Martin (1984). The notion has been established in the framework of systemic functional linguistics (SFL) (see Halliday, 1994). Central to SFL is a focus on the meaning-making potential of texts, the choices available in language use, and the relationship between texts and their contexts. SFL researchers argue that language use is shaped by the social and cultural contexts in which it occurs (see e.g., Butt et al., 2012; Martin & Rose, 2008). Martin (1984) originally defined genre as "*a staged, goal-oriented, purposeful activity*" that is characteristic of specific communities (p. 25). This

definition remains the prevailing understanding of genre in SFL (see e.g., Martin, 2016; Gardner, 2017).

Genre-based writing pedagogy employs a teaching-learning cycle (see Hammond et al., 1992). The cycle consists of four stages designed to scaffold learners' writing development. In stage 1, *building knowledge of the field*, learners develop an understanding of a cultural or social context and lexical and grammatical patterns of the target genre. In stage 2, *modelling of text*, learners are presented with a model text, along with an explanation of its text structure and linguistic features. In the next stage, *joint construction of text*, teachers scaffold learners as they work together to complete a task related to the target genre. The final stage, *independent construction of text*, requires learners to construct a text autonomously.

Genre-based writing pedagogy and teacher development

Recent studies have explored teacher development with a focus on genre-based writing pedagogy. For example, Dinh and Nguyen (2023) examined how Vietnamese K-12 and university English language teachers resisted and adapted genre-based writing pedagogy following a five-week workshop on the approach. Although the workshop motivated teachers toward professional development, many participants perceived implementing the pedagogy in their teaching as impractical. This was attributed to limited preparation time for a new teaching approach and the necessity to focus on sentence-level grammatical knowledge assessed in national exams. Mulyono et al. (2023) conducted an online, five-session workshop on genre-based writing for language teachers in Indonesia. They evaluated the development of their academic writing skills using pre- and post-tests. The study found that short-term instruction did not significantly enhance the teachers' academic writing creativity. The researchers concluded that language teachers could benefit more from long-term support.

While genre-based writing pedagogy has demonstrated effectiveness in developing learners' writing proficiency, more research is needed to understand how educators can acquire the knowledge and skills required to implement this approach in their teaching settings. As Nagao (2019) argues (see the Introduction section), it is essential to determine which aspects of genre-based writing pedagogy are beneficial for teachers. Analysing teachers' perspectives offers valuable insights for advancing this pedagogical approach.

The research sets out to explore three research questions.

1. What are a teacher's perspectives on adopting genre-based writing pedagogy?
2. What are the valuable aspects of genre-based writing pedagogy for the teacher?
3. What are the challenges in adopting genre-based writing pedagogy for the teacher?

METHODOLOGY

This longitudinal case study employed a qualitative approach to examine a language teacher's perspectives on and practices of genre-based writing pedagogy. A longitudinal case study approach was selected as it aligned with the study's objective of providing an in-depth portrayal of the teacher's implementation of genre-based pedagogy. Data were collected through the participant's journal and interviews with the participant.

Data collection

This study investigated the attitudes and practices of an English language teacher in Japan regarding genre-based writing pedagogy over one year. The teacher, who worked in a public high school (years 10 to 12) in central Japan, was selected as the participant. The study was conducted in Japan, exploring how genre-based writing pedagogy is employed in an EFL context. The participant was chosen since he was experienced and well-qualified as a language teacher with a Master of Education degree in TESOL. With such experience and qualification, he could adopt genre-based writing pedagogy and reflect on its usefulness and challenges. By exploring his practices and perspectives, the research aimed to generate insights into both the possibilities and challenges of implementing genre-based writing pedagogy in a Japanese context. The researcher provided the participant with three seminars on genre-based writing pedagogy and held additional meetings as needed to support material and lesson development. However, the participant was not required to adopt the seminar content and retained full autonomy over lesson planning. To analyse the participant's perspectives and practices, data were collected through his journal entries (see Table 1) and interviews (See Table 2).

Table 1. A list of journal entries

Journal entry number	Time of submission
Journal entry 1	June, 2022
Journal entry 2	September, 2022
Journal entry 3	December, 2022

Table 2. A list of interviews

Interview number	Time of interview
Interview 1	July, 2022
Interview 2	February, 2023

Data analysis

The journal and interview data were analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis framework. To ensure the reliability of the interview data, all interviews were transcribed. The journal and interview data were analysed twice, with intervals between the coding sessions. The analysis followed six stages: familiarising with the data, generating codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report. The questions used in the journals and interviews are presented in the Appendix. Additional questions were incorporated during the interviews to clarify the interviewee's comments.

FINDINGS

Answers relevant to research question 1 (Teacher's perspectives on genre-based writing pedagogy)

Journals

The journal data reveal that the teacher's attitudes towards genre-based writing pedagogy evolved as he received theoretical input from the author and applied it

to his teaching. Initially, in the first journal entry submitted in June 2022, the participant did not recognise the significance of theoretical input for his teaching, as indicated by the comment: *“When practising writing instruction, the target audience and instructional context vary. Therefore, it is difficult to solve instructional challenges based solely on theory”* (translated by the author). However, by the third journal entry in December 2022, he acknowledged that understanding genres could be beneficial in designing writing tasks. He also perceived genre-based writing pedagogy as effective in developing learners’ writing skills by stating, *“I think that the consistency of instruction has improved by setting the task content considering factors such as genre, linguistic features, and difficulty”* (translated by the author).

Interviews

The interview data analysis showed a change in the participant's perspectives on genre-based writing pedagogy from the first to the second interview. In the first interview, conducted in July 2022, the participant emphasised writing topics and sentence-level grammar. By the second interview in February 2023, however, he prioritised different types of genres and the teaching-learning cycle central to genre-based writing pedagogy in his teaching. This is exemplified in his comment, *“By studying how different types of genres have different purposes and linguistic features, I think the clarity of setting goals for writing instruction have significantly improved”* (translated by the author).

Answers relevant to research question 2 (Useful aspects of genre-based writing pedagogy)

Journals

The journal data illustrated how the participant recognised the effective aspects of genre-based writing pedagogy. In the second and third journal entries, he reflected on using the concept of genre to design writing tasks, such as creating a descriptive genre task. In the third journal, he discussed the advantages of adopting the teaching-learning cycle central to genre-based writing pedagogy, positively evaluating all four stages of the cycle as he wrote, *“I thought that the effectiveness of instruction could be expected by carrying out all the stages of genre-based pedagogy”* (translated by the author).

Interviews

The interview data highlight how the participant benefited from genre-based writing pedagogy. He found the lexical and grammatical features specific to each genre valuable for his learners. He also commented on the usefulness of Stage 2, *modelling of text*, in the teaching-learning cycle, noting that it clarified his learners' expectations for each writing task. This can be observed in his statement in the second interview, "*Since I had never consciously taught the grammatical features of descriptive writing, the way I present input (linguistic features) to students has completely changed*" (translated and explanation added by the author).

Answers relevant to research question 3 (Challenges in adopting genre-based writing pedagogy)*Journals*

The journal data revealed some challenges the participant faced when implementing genre-based writing pedagogy in his teaching context, with time being the most significant hindrance. In the second journal entry, he acknowledged that there was insufficient time to conduct a writing lesson and provide feedback during Stage 4 of the teaching-learning cycle, *independent construction of text*. He stated, "*Since it takes time to provide corrections, it is very difficult to carry them out in a detailed and thorough manner due to time constraints*" (translated by the author). To cope with this challenge, the participant used an AI feedback tool, EasyBib (Chegg Service, 2024), to assist in providing feedback. Since providing feedback to students was a challenge in his teaching context, the tool was helpful for the teacher in delivering corrective feedback to approximately 100 learners.

Interviews

The participant also discussed challenges in adopting genre-based writing pedagogy in the interviews. In the second interview, he noted the need to include a reflection activity in which learners reflect on their writing and writing process, as promoted by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology-Japan (MEXT) to foster learner autonomy. He expressed that finding time for this within the teaching-learning cycle of genre-based writing pedagogy was challenging. Additionally, class size was crucial in selecting a teaching approach, as he taught multiple classes of 40 learners each. The participant also indicated that considerable input and support were necessary to fully understand and implement the pedagogy in his teaching. This can be observed in the participant's comment in

the second interview, *“I was able to take on these new challenges because I had support from a university professor. It would likely be difficult without such support”* (translated by the author).

DISCUSSION

The study examined changes in the participant’s perspectives on genre-based writing pedagogy. Initially, he was sceptical about its applicability within his teaching context. However, as he integrated his own ideas with those embedded in the pedagogy, he began perceiving its value. This shift is significant for teacher development, as identity transformation plays a crucial role in this process (see Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009). These findings suggest that longitudinal and reflective research can facilitate and document teacher identity and professional development changes. The findings show that continuous support and consultation may be essential for effectively adopting genre-based writing pedagogy in a teaching context, as short-term support may not significantly contribute to teachers’ development (Mulyono et al., 2023). The participant articulated the challenges in comprehending the pedagogy and its underlying theories. The online and in-person seminars and meetings held with the participant over a year facilitated the integration of this pedagogy into his teaching.

The findings merit discussion regarding the application of genre-based writing pedagogy in a Japanese context and its implications for teacher development. The variety of genres and the structured teaching-learning cycle benefited both the teacher participant and his learners. Notably, it took time for the participant to fully adopt genre-based writing pedagogy, implementing it only after carefully considering learners’ needs and the instructional requirements set by MEXT. This aligns with findings from Dinh and Nguyen’s (2023) research. MEXT, for example, promotes reflection activities within lessons, prompting the participant to incorporate a reflection activity into the teaching-learning cycle of genre-based writing pedagogy.

The findings indicate that genre-based writing pedagogy requires adaptation when implemented in a Japanese teaching context. Specifically, while the first three stages of the pedagogy were effective, modifications were necessary for the fourth stage, the independent construction of text. The participant found it challenging to provide corrective feedback at this stage due to the large class size of approximately 100 learners, despite feedback being a crucial component. To address this issue, he incorporated the AI-based corrective feedback tool EasyBib

(Chegg Service, 2024) into students' independent learning outside the classroom. This tool generates revised versions of texts focusing on sentence-level grammar and vocabulary (see Stevenson & Phakiti, 2019, for insights on automated feedback in writing). Using this tool, the participant could focus his feedback on content and text structure in students' writing.

Although only one teacher participated in this study, the findings may be relevant to other teaching contexts, particularly in EFL settings. Challenges related to class size and the educational activities required by local authorial institutions in implementing genre-based writing pedagogy may arise in various contexts. The study highlights the critical role of teachers in balancing pedagogical principles, such as genre-based writing pedagogy, with the specific needs and demands of their local teaching environments.

CONCLUSIONS

Both the genre types and the four stages of the teaching-learning cycle were applicable in this context, bringing new perspectives to English language writing instruction for the participant. However, the pedagogy required modifications to align with the specific teaching context and MEXT requirements. The issue of limited time for the *independent construction of text* stage was addressed using an AI text correction tool, and a reflection stage was added to meet MEXT's emphasis on learner autonomy. Regarding teacher development, long-term, continuous support proved essential for successfully implementing the pedagogy. A limitation of this research is the small sample size; further studies with a more significant number of participants are needed to deepen understanding of how genre-based writing pedagogy can be effectively applied in a Japanese context. This relates to the research method and case study employed in the article. As Casanave (2015) points out, case studies are not suitable for research on a population of people; therefore, the findings of the current study should inform future research involving a more representative group of teachers and their experiences and perspectives on genre-based pedagogy.

AUTHOR

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THE APPENDIX

Questions asked in journals and interviews

1. What do you think is important in writing instruction?
2. What theoretical foundations do you think support the above-mentioned important aspects of instruction?
3. Do you think theoretical foundations are important in writing instruction? Why do you think so?
4. Is it easy or difficult for teachers currently working in schools to learn about theoretical foundations? Why do you think so?
5. What aspects of genre-based writing pedagogy (text types, characteristics of written language, grammatical and lexical features of persuasive writing) do you find useful in high school writing instruction?
6. What aspects of genre-based writing pedagogy do you find less useful in high school writing instruction?
7. If you have incorporated genre theory into writing instruction, how did you feel about it?
8. If you have incorporated genre theory into writing instruction, do you think it brought any changes to the learners?